

IMPACT RESPONSE OF CARBON/EPOXY PLATES

Y. Qian and S.R. Swanson

(Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Utah, Salt Lake City, Utah 84112, USA)

ABSTRACT

The response of carbon/epoxy laminates to impact is a problem of much interest due to the sensitivity of these materials to accidental damage. The complexity of the problem suggests that a combined experimental and analytical approach is required. In the present study impact experiments were carried out to determine the applicability of scaling rules so that the response of large structures could be related to laboratory tests. Plate specimens were employed, ranging in size by a factor of five. Measured strains were found to follow the scaling rules quite closely. Theoretical analyses of the impact agreed very well with experiment, and supported the conclusions of the experiments regarding scaling rules.

INTRODUCTION

The response of carbon/epoxy laminates to transverse impact is of much importance due to the susceptibility of these materials to delamination and fiber breakage under impact loading. The complexity of the impact event and resulting damage suggests that a combination of analysis and experiment will be required to fully understand the problem. Despite a number of previous studies on impact in composite materials, it is clear that further work is required. In the present study an experimental investigation is made into the impact response of carbon/epoxy plates with particular emphasis on scaling of results to structures of different sizes, so that insight into the impact response of large scale structures can be obtained from laboratory experiments on small scale specimens.

A number of previous studies have been carried out on the impact response of structures. Studies have been conducted on impact of plates by Sun et al. [1-5], and other investigators [6-9]. Analyses have been conducted by Dobyns [10], Sun et al. [1-4], and Cairns and Lagace [11].

As shown by Dobyns [10], the response of a plate to a suddenly applied force can easily be calculated if the plate boundary conditions are those of simple support. In this case the usual Navier solution can be obtained by expanding the displacements and rotations as well as the load in appropriate Fourier series. It has been emphasized by a number of investigators that transverse shear effects must be included in the analysis. While the results of Dobyns give insight into the structural response, in general in impact the force loading is not known but must be calculated as part of the solution. Sun and Chattopadhyay [2] show that applying the equations of rigid body dynamics to the impactor permits the impact force to be related to the motion of the impactor. Sun et al. [1-5] have also included the effects of the indentation at the contact point, and show by experiments that the contact stiffness for laminates can be obtained from a Hertz analysis.

Boundary conditions other than simple support have been analyzed by means of a Rayleigh-Ritz procedure, using assumed mode shapes based on combinations of the modes for beams. The procedure has been outlined by Vinson and Sierakowski [12], and recently employed by Cairns and Lagace [11].

The question of scaling of the dynamic response is important in extrapolating laboratory results to large structures. This subject has been considered by Morton [13], who discussed a number of complications in scaling results. For example, in geometric scaling without explicit consideration of time effects, the change in time scale with geometric scaling may bring in differences in response due to viscoelastic effects in matrix deformation.

In the following, the experiments on impact of plates of different sizes are described in detail. An analysis of the structural response is then presented. Finally, comparisons are given between the experiments and the analysis.

EXPERIMENTS

The experiments were carried out on plates made of AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy, using five sizes of plates that were geometrically scaled. The plates ranged in size from 50 mm by 37.5 mm by 1.072 mm thick to 250 by 187.5 mm by 5.36 mm thick. If the scale parameter is termed λ , the dimensions of the plates were thus scaled by $\lambda=1,2,3,4$, and 5. The layup was $[(\pm 72)_m/0_{2m}]_s$, with $m=\lambda$, the scaling factor.

A special compressed air gun was constructed for the impact experiments. The projectiles were cylinders, constructed in five different diameters which were scaled with the same geometric parameter as the plates. The impact end of the projectile was hemispherical, but with three different radii for each of the five different impactors. The mass of each projectile was thus scaled as λ^3 . The use of cylindrical projectiles instead of the more usual spherical projectiles had several important advantages. It permitted independent variation of the impactor mass and contact shape. It also facilitated a highly repeatable apparatus, as the impact velocity could be accurately controlled. This is believed due to the tighter seal around the cylinder relative to a sphere, while being accelerated down the barrel of the compressed air gun.

The velocity of the impactor was measured by the breaking and making of a light beam produced by a light emitting diode, located near the end of the barrel. Strains were measured on the surface of the specimens with resistance strain gages, and recorded with a high speed digital data acquisition system. The sizes of the strain gages were scaled along with the plate sizes. Each strain gaged specimen was subjected to an impact at a low velocity, followed by impact at a higher velocity intended to produce damage in the specimen.

The plate specimens were clamped on two opposing edges and were free on the other two edges. The clamped edges were normal to the 0 degree fibers, and the direction of these fibers is designated as the X direction.

ANALYSIS

Because of the use of clamped boundary conditions on two opposing edges of the plate and free boundaries on the other two edges in the experiments, equations were developed using the Rayleigh-Ritz procedure. The Rayleigh-Ritz procedure is based on the use of "beam functions", which are mode shapes from solutions to beam equations with the appropriate boundary conditions. The assumed deformed shape of the plate is then taken as a product of these functions.

The analysis is based on Lagrange's equation of motion, using $L=T-V$. The potential energy V is given as

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \iint_A [\kappa]^T [D] [\kappa] dA + \frac{1}{2} \iint_A [\gamma]^T [A] [\gamma] dA - \iint_A p(t,x,y) w(t,x,y) dA \quad (1)$$

where the energy includes both bending and transverse shear effects. The notation follows that of Vinson and Sierakowski [12]. The kinetic energy of the plate is given by

$$T = \frac{\rho h}{2} \iint_A \dot{w}(t,x,y) dA \quad (2)$$

Here the inplane and rotation inertia effects have been neglected, as suggested by Bert and Birman [14] and Dobyns [10].

For rectangular plates, the series approximation for the rotations and transverse displacements can be taken as

$$\bar{\alpha}(t, x, y) = \sum_m \sum_n A_{mn}(t) X_m'(x) Y_n(y)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\beta}(t, x, y) &= \sum_m \sum_n B_{mn}(t) X_m(x) Y_n'(y) \\ w(t, x, y) &= \sum_m \sum_n C_{mn}(t) X_m(x) Y_n(y)\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where A_{mn} , B_{mn} , C_{mn} are the mode amplitudes of the plate and are to be determined. Substituting the assumed mode shapes in the expressions for potential and kinetic energy, and then using Lagrange's equations gives the equations of motion. Substituting A and B in terms of C into the third equation, gives the second order ordinary differential equation for the modal amplitudes

$$S \ddot{C} + T C = P \quad (4)$$

In the present study the assumed mode shapes are taken as beam functions, which are solutions for mode shapes of beams under the appropriate boundary conditions [15]. The beam functions are orthogonal, permitting expansion of the load in terms of these functions. The P in Eqn 4 is a force term, and each component comes from taking the derivative of the work done by the lateral load to the relative mode amplitude, that is

$$P_{mn} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial C_{mn}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial C_{mn}} \iint_A p(t,x,y) w(t,x,y) dA = \iint_A p(t,x,y) X_m(x) Y_n(y) dA \quad (5)$$

The contact force is assumed to be related to the contact indentation by the following eqn, following Sun et al. [1-5]

$$p_0 = k (\alpha)^{3/2} \quad \text{with} \quad k = \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{R_s} E_{22} \quad (6)$$

where p_0 is the total force on the plate and α is the local indentation.

The contact force is then related to the motion of the projectile by assuming rigid body dynamics for the projectile. Due to the nonlinearity of the contact deformation relationship, the above equations were solved numerically, using the Newmark beta method with $\beta=1/4$, which gives an unconditionally stable solution.

RESULTS

As described above, tests were carried out at 4 impact velocities on 5 sizes of specimens, using 3 different impact tup diameters. The major features of the experimental results, along with comparisons from the analysis, will be presented here.

Fig 1 shows the strain response of the 100 mm plate to the 3.18, 6.35, and 12.7 diameter impact tups, at an impact velocity of 4.57 m/s. The response shows the dynamics of the response, as well as indicating a relatively small effect of the tup diameter. Clearly the contact stiffness, which varies with the impact tup size as shown in Eqn 6 does not play a major role in the response. This lack of sensitivity to the contact stiffness was also observed in the analysis results. The comparison of measured and predicted strain on the back side of the plate at the impact point is shown in Fig 2. It can be seen that the strain compares very well between analysis and experiment. The predicted period is somewhat less than the measured value, which was observed in all of the comparisons.

In an attempt to verify that the experiments followed the scaling rules, the response of the Y direction strain for plates of sizes $\lambda=1,3,$ and 5 are shown in Fig 3. The results indicate that the strains in the different size plates exhibit the same response if time is scaled by $1/\lambda$, as indicated by the scaling. Clearly this is a strong verification of the scaling rules.

The results shown thus far have been at impact velocities of 4.6 m/s, which is low enough so that damage was not observed either visibly or by C-scan inspection. Fig 4 shows the peak strains measured at higher velocities. The results are both quite scattered and also exhibit a softening nonlinearity at the

highest impact velocities. This is not surprising, as extensive damage could be observed at these higher velocities. In fact, the X direction strain gages typically failed before termination of the test.

DISCUSSION

The major objectives of the present work are two-fold; to compare the experimentally measured response in the different sized plates with scaling rules, and to compare the analysis with the experiments. As mentioned above, the experiments were designed so that impact at the same velocity would give the same peak strains but the time scale would vary inversely with the geometric scale factor λ , if the simple scaling rules hold. This was accomplished by scaling the dimensions of the plates, impactor, and strain gage sizes by λ (over a range of 5), and by scaling the impactor mass as λ^3 . However in more detail, certain factors of the experiments either were not scaled or would not be expected to scale in the same way. As discussed by Morton [13] for example, the diameter of the carbon fibers does not change. Perhaps more importantly, the contact stiffness law is nonlinear and does not follow the simple geometric scaling rules. Further, any possible viscoelastic effects in the matrix would be affected by time and thus would not follow the scaling rules. Thus the test of scaling of the response is really a test of the relative importance of these effects in the overall structural response.

The experimental results show that scaling holds very well. Fig 3 is quite convincing in demonstrating the lack of effect of the absolute size in the response at relatively low strain levels. This result is supported by the insensitivity of the experimental results to the diameter of the impact tip. These results were also supported by the calculations, in that the calculations also showed insensitivity to the details of the contact zone. For example, little difference was observed in the predicted overall structural response if the contact zone were held constant in size throughout the calculation, instead of the presumably more accurate procedure of increasing the contact zone size as the contact force increased. As discussed by Cairns and Lagace [16], the details of the contact loading may influence the stresses in the immediate vicinity of the contact zone. However the present results indicate that the effect is much less on the overall structural response, including strains as measured by strain gages on the back side of the impact site.

The comparison of analytical prediction with experiment is excellent at low velocities. The number of assumed modes, which ranged from 9 by 9 to 15 by 15, is clearly sufficient to give good accuracy for strains. It may also be noted that the clamped-clamped and free-free boundary conditions used in the experimental study are more difficult to analyze than are simple support conditions. They were selected at present in order to make the strain distributions in the plates appropriate for a particular structure of interest.

The major conclusion of the present work is that the strains in the composite plates closely follow the simple scaling rules obtained from the linear differential equations of motion. The next step in the overall program is to compare the degree of damage incurred in the impact over the range of sizes of the composite plates.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Impact experiments have been carried out on carbon/epoxy composite plates in which the geometry of the plates was scaled by factors up to five. The experimentally measured strains closely followed scaling rules obtained from the linear equations of motion, indicating that the nonlinear contact stiffness did not appreciably influence the structural response. Dynamic analyses using a Rayleigh-Ritz technique compared well with the experiments, indicating good accuracy in predicting strains in the impacted plates.

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Fig. 1. Measured ϵ_x behind impact point in 100mm by 75mm plate for three tup sizes, $V_0 = 4.57\text{m/s}$.

Fig. 2. Comparison of analysis with experiment for ϵ_x in 100mm by 75mm plate, $V_0 = 4.57\text{m/s}$.

Fig. 3. Comparison of strain response in impact test on three different size plates, showing time scaling, $V_0 = 4.57\text{m/s}$.

Fig. 4. Effect of impact velocity on ϵ_y for five different plate sizes.